

INTEGRATED THERMAL, MICRO-MECHANICAL AND STRUCTURAL MODELLING OF POST-FIRE BEHAVIOUR OF FIRE RETARDANT STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Integrated modelling of fire retardant structural composites is presented in this paper. It incorporates the outcomes of analyses from chemical kinetics, heat-mass transfer, micro/meso-mechanics into macroscopic analysis of structures of polymeric composites exposed to elevated temperatures so that the post-fire performances and structural integrity of such structures can be assessed.

Keywords: Fire retardant structural composites; Post-fire behaviour; micro-mechanical modelling; Unit cells; Effective properties

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric matrix composites are widely used in aerospace, automotive, sporting equipment and civil constructions because of their high specific strength and stiffness and other favourable mechanical and physicochemical properties. However, their flammability is seen as one of their disadvantages because of their chemical structures. The flammability of them means that smoke and toxic gases may be released from them during combustion. In the meantime, the structural integrity may be compromise. This has to be taken into account for safe use of such materials in engineering structures where fire is a potential hazard. A feasible way to improve the fire resistance of polymer matrix composites is to add fire retardant additives, *viz.* visil (cellulosic charring agent) and intumescent (melamine phosphate), in the matrix of the composite [1-5]. In the present work, modelling of post-fire performance of fire retardant composites at both material and at structural levels is presented, incorporating the outcomes from chemical kinetics and heat-mass transfer analyses. It has also been validated through systematic experiments correspondingly.

THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENTS

The overall objective of the research is to formulate an integrated predictive modelling tool for the prediction of residual mechanical properties of fire retarded composites after exposure to elevated temperatures. The tool consists of modules across disciplines. A

physicochemical model has been developed by partners at Bolton University for chemical and thermal behaviours in response to elevated temperatures. As the research is primarily for glass fibres reinforced composites, within the temperature range interested, the change in the properties of the fibres is negligible. The changes will be solely from the polymeric resin as the matrix for the composites. The associated issues in this respect include softening at elevated temperatures, chemical disintegration with discharge of volatiles accompanied with mass loss from the resin and char formation where fire retardant additives play a crucial role. The output of the above analysis will be fed into a series sequential micro-, meso- and macro-mechanical models to obtain effective properties of composites after exposure to elevated temperature and ultimately to predict the performances of structures of composites experienced fire damage to different extents.

Simulations at materials level

The chemical kinetics and heat and mass transfer of the composite as it is exposed to a range of heat flux levels has been analysed in [6] as the other part of the project. Out of these analyses, the temperature distributions in the composites have been obtained theoretically which have also been validated through experiments. Some of the results are presented at the same conference in a different paper by partners at Bolton University. The composite mass variations with temperature experienced as obtained from TGA tests on composite samples are shown in Fig. 1(a). They can be reasonably closely reproduced theoretically as reported in a companion paper [6] as a module of the integrated modelling technique. The chemical disintegration process in the resin at elevated temperature produces volatiles. Those trapped inside after cooling down can be treated as microscopic voids in the resin. The resin can then be considered as a porous material effectively. For porous materials, there is a well established quadratic relationship between the effective (residual) Young's modulus of the porous material and the porosity or the relative density [7]. This is adopted here.

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = k \left(\frac{M_R}{M_0} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where E_0 and E are the Young's modulus of matrix before and after exposure to elevated temperature, k is a material constant which should be determined experimentally, M_R and M_0 are the residual and initial masses of matrix. Since the pure matrix samples were not easy to make, especially for those with additives, the tests were conducted on composite samples. For composite samples, available experimental data suggested that the following relationship give a reasonable prediction of the effective resin property.

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = (M_c - M_f - M_a)^2 \quad (2)$$

where M_c the residual mass of composite, M_f the mass of fibre, M_a the residual mass of additives. The residual Young's modulus of matrix thus obtained is shown in Fig. 1(b).

The mechanical properties of visil additives are similar to those of the resin and they are treated as resin. The mechanical properties of intumescent additives are negligible in comparison with those of the resin and the spaces occupied by them are treated as voids. The intumescent additives to the resin are apparently unhelpful at low temperatures.

Their presence is equivalent to voids suspended in the matrix effectively. After experiencing high temperatures, the trend reverses, although values of obtained residual Young's moduli with additives are only slightly above that without additives. In reality, the slight residual Young's modulus retained represents the contribution of char formed during the chemical degradation process. Although the quantity of the char formed from the additives is very small, it tends to hold the fibres together to a degree as a binder, which could make significant difference in the performance of the composite as compared with loose fibre.

Fig. 1 (a) Mass variation (b) Residual Young's modulus of matrix, extracted from composites with and without additives exposed to elevated temperatures

There are 9 engineering constants for an orthotropic material and they have to be predicted after exposure to different temperatures. Use can be made of unit cells based micro-and meso-mechanical models [8]. A microscale unit cell is employed to obtain effective properties of the yarn as a unidirectional composite. A mesoscale unit cell is then employed to accommodate yarns according to the actual woven pattern with the rest of the space filled with the matrix. With a plain weave as employed in the experiments, the composite exhibits orthotropic characteristics. The effective material parameters of the composites can be evaluated as shown in Fig. 2(a)-(c). The residual Young's modulus of matrix after exposure to elevated temperature as obtained above has been used.

Simulation at structural level

The micro- and meso-mechanical models can be used to predict post-fire effective material properties of fire retarded composites. The objective is to feed such effective properties into structural analyses where different part of the structure may have experienced different extent of elevated temperatures. To demonstrate this, a series of analyses have been made to laminated panels of fire retarded composite having a fire damaged zone due to exposure to different heat fluxes for different durations. The dimensions of the finite element model are 214mm long, 117mm wide and 2.8mm thick for panel without additives but 3.2mm thick for panel with additives. The temperature distributions in the composites have been obtained theoretically which have also been validated through experiments. The models as described in the previous subsection have been employed to evaluate the effective properties of composite in the damaged zone in different laminae. Continuum shell elements (with 4 layers) were employed for the FE analysis. The mesh is shown in Fig. 3. The panel is clamped along three edges while the fourth edge is left free. A concentrated load is applied through rigid

hemispherical indenter close to the free edge but away from the damaged zone. The contact condition between the panel and the indenter has been simulated. The results will be presented later and compared with experiments which have also been conducted in order to validate the theory.

Fig. 2 Predicted material properties of the composites (a) Young's moduli, (b) Poisson ratios, (c) shear moduli, (d) In-plane Young's modulus compared with experimental data (flexural modulus, with A standing for additives)

Fig. 3 The FE mesh

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Systematic experiments have been carried out at materials and structural levels. Some of them were intended to extract necessary material properties to facilitate the theoretical modelling while others were for validation of the theoretical models.

Study at materials level

The material under consideration is woven E-glass-fibre-reinforced composites of epoxy matrix with appropriate amount of flame retardant additives in forms of visil and intumescent. For all composite specimens tested, the weight fraction of the glass fibre was kept at 50% nominally. Using the densities of the glass fibre and resin as 2.5 and 1.1 kg/m³, respectively, and assuming intumescent and visil sharing the same density as the resin, the fibre volume fraction for these specimens can be found as 30.6%. The results as shown in Fig. 4(a) suggest that at 575°C the composite without additives lose 50% of its mass. This means that only fibres in the composite are left. When the matrix is modified with fire retardant additives, the composite exhibits reduced mass loss due to the exposure to elevate temperatures because of the resistance to oxidation and the enhancement of char formation from the additives. The residual flexural moduli of the composites with and without additives after cooling down from a range of elevated temperatures were measured through three-point bending tests. The results are shown in Fig. 4(b). While the weight fractions are used in the keys in Fig.4(a) for the ease of relating to mass loss, the volume fractions as converted from weight fractions are adopted in the keys in Fig.4(b) for conventional use in theoretical studies. In Fig. 4(b), there is a steep drop of residual flexural modulus between 375°C and 425°C because at this stage matrix disintegrates chemically and the samples lose their load bearing capability against bending as a result. Due to the flammability of the epoxy resin, ignition can take place at high temperatures. Mass loss varies greatly with the duration of combustion which increases the complexity of the problem.

Fig. 4 Experimental data (a) mass variation from TGA at 10°C/min in air (b) residual flexural modulus versus temperature (F, R, V and I stand for fibre, resin, visil and intumescent, respectively)

Study at structural level

Composite panels as small scale structures without (control sample) and with fire retardant additives (10% weight fraction of visil and 10% weight fraction of intumescent) were made for a series of tests to investigate the structural behaviour of fire damaged composites. The specimens were exposed to heat flux 35kw/m² for 3 minutes under a cone calorimeter within a designated local region in the specimens. Two of them have been shown in Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b). The panel with additives, Fig. 5(b), is more opaque than the control sample, Fig. 5(a). The nominal in-plane dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig. 5(c). The average thicknesses for the

panels without and with additives are 2.8mm and 3.2mm, respectively. They were to be clamped to a rigid frame along three edges while leaving one of the longitudinal edges free. To facilitate this, 9 holes were drilled along the three edges to be clamped, as shown in Fig. 5, so that bolts could be employed to fix the clampers along these edges to fulfil a clamped condition during the test. The loading point is at the central axis 15mm away from the free edge and hence outside the heat damaged zone. The load is applied through a rigid hemispherical indenter with a diameter of 15mm.

Fig. 5 Composite panels (a) without and (b) with additives (c) in-plane dimensions

A circular area of 50mm diameter centred at the central axis but 60mm away from the free edge was designated for each specimen for exposure to heat flux. The specimens were exposed to two different levels of heat flux for each of which two different durations of heating time (heat flux 13kw/m^2 for 3 minutes and 9 minutes and heat flux 35kw/m^2 for 2 minutes and 3 minutes). These were conducted under a cone calorimeter. The surface of the part of the specimen including the back outside of the designated circular area was insulated with ceramic wool. Several thermal couples were placed on the surface and embedded between layers in the composite specimens for measuring the temperature profile through the thickness of the panel during the heating test.

After the heat exposure, the panels were taken out of the cone calorimeter and cooled down to ambient temperature. These heat damaged specimens were then tested mechanically for their structural performances. Six strain gauge rosettes were placed on the composite panel as indicated by crosses in Fig. 5(c). Positions I, III, V and VI were on the loading side while II and IV were on the back side. The tests were conducted using an Instron machine. The specimens deflected under loading. The deflection at loading point was recorded as the crosshead displacement. The load-deflection curve was thus recorded as shown in Fig. 6(a) for panels without additives and Fig. 6(b) for panels with additives. The range of loading went beyond the small deflection regime. As a result, significant nonlinearity was observed showing a stiffening behaviour due to the clamped boundary supports. Strains were recorded from the strain gauges attached. The same procedure was applied to all the specimens.

Towards the end of each test at excessive deflection, the specimen started to delaminate, initially around the middle of the free edge and propagate gradually. The initiation and propagation of delamination were reflected in the load-deflection curves as small load drops, resulting in the relaxation of the stiffening behaviour as shown in Fig. 6. These were followed by a more catastrophic mode of failure which was a transverse crack appearing first at the middle of the free edge. This defined the load carrying capacity of the specimen under test as associated with this there was a significant load drop in the load-deflection curve and the load levelled off afterwards as clearly shown in Fig. 5 as the crack propagated along the central axis.

Fig. 6 load-displacement curves in comparison with finite element analyses (a) without additives, (b) with additives, (c) both without and with additives (d) initial slope of the displacement-load curves for panels without and with additives

RESULTS, COMPARISONS AND DISCUSSION

The elastic modulus obtained from the tests and predictions have been compared in Fig. 2(d). Good agreement is observed for temperatures up to 400°C. When the composite is exposed to higher temperatures, significant discrepancies are found. This is primarily due to the difference between types of the elastic modulus under comparison. The predicted one is tensile elastic modulus while in experiments flexural modulus measured. When a composite loses its matrix, tensile stiffness survives to a much greater extent than the bending stiffness. This explains the discrepancies in Fig. 2(d).

The load-deflection curves of the composite panels exposed to different heat fluxes and heating times have been shown in Fig. 6. The panels with additives tended to be slightly stiffer than those without additives when their load-deflection curves are plotted together in Fig. 6(c). This was purely due to the increased thickness of the panels with

additives. FE predictions were made up to about 10mm deflection. Since there was no mechanisms, such as delamination and fibre fracture, were included in the FE model, while the behaviour beyond this level is dominated by these feature, predictions beyond this level would not be very meaningful. Within this range, the trend is captured precisely by the FE prediction and the comparisons between FE and experiments are excellent. FE produced very similar load-deflection curves for panels exposed to different heat flux and different heating time the relationships. This was because the heat accumulated from radiation before ignition was not significant enough to cause mechanical property degradation to show up in the overall appearance of the load-deflection curves. Although all curves seem to cluster together, the initial slopes of the load-deflection curves as predicted through the FE analyses for the panels with and without additive suggest noticeable difference. The initial slopes of the load-deflection curves for composite panels without and with additives exposed to heat flux 35kw/m^2 at different heating time have been interpolated from the results of the first increment as shown in Fig. 6(d). The crossover at about 6 minutes of exposure between the two curves reconfirms the difference the additives make. While the additive tend to undermine the stiffness of the composite with low incident heat, the strengthening effect is observed at high incident heat. The structural integrity of the panels with additives is better kept for panels with additives after 6 minutes exposure to 35kw/m^2 heat flux. The retardation effect of the additives against elevated temperatures has been demonstrated.

During the tests, the strains were recorded via six strain rosettes. As strains are more directly related to the prescribed deflection, differences are insignificant between the strains from specimens exposed to different heat fluxes and heating times. The all look like those shown in Fig. 7 at different positions of the composite panels. The comparisons between experimental and numerical simulations also show extremely good agreement within the range where predictions were made, which validates the simulation from another perspective.

CONCLUSIONS

Predictions of the post-fire mechanical performances of fire retardant structural composites have been pursued from a microscopic scale to a macroscopic scale. Micro-mechanical modelling using unit cells has been carried out to obtain residual elastic properties of the composites after exposure to elevated temperatures. Such obtained properties have then been used in macroscopic structural analyses to assess the post-fire performances of structures made of such composites. The modelling strategy has been validated at both materials and structural levels by systematic experimental data.

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 7 In-plane strains at different positions (a) strain gauge rosette I, (b) rosette II, (c) rosette III, (d) rosette IV, (e) rosette V, (f) rosette VI

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